

Familial Speckled Acral Hypopigmentation in Two Successive Generations – A Rare Case Report

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Abstract:

Speckled acral hypopigmentation is a rare entity. Familial cases have been reported that are similar to our case. It falls under reticulate acropigmentation disorders, along with reticulate acropigmentation of Kitamura (RAPK), reticulate acropigmentation of Dohi (RAPD), Dyschromatosis universalis hereditaria (DUH) and acromelanosis albo-punctata. Other clinical differential diagnoses include Dowling-Degos disease, congenital symmetric acral leukopathy, and Confetti macules of tuberous sclerosis. Speckled acral hypopigmentation can be differentiated by the presence of small hypopigmented macules over acral areas with clustering, the absence of hyperpigmented macules, palmar pits and neurological complaints etc. On woods lamp examination, there will be no accentuation. An increased number of macromelanosomes, both in melanocytes and keratinocytes and a decreased or normal number of melanocytes can be seen on histopathological examination. As there are very few case reports, we report one such case of Familial speckled acral hypopigmentation in two successive generations.

Keywords: Dyschromatosis, Speckled, Acral Hypopigmentation, Reticulate Pigmentary Disorders.

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Introduction

Case Report: A 17-year-old male patient born to first-degree consanguineous parents presented with complaints of asymptomatic, small, white spots on bilateral feet since four months.

The patient noticed white spots on his feet four months ago. On keen examination, his parents found innumerable tiny, white spots on his feet. The number of lesions remained the same. On cutaneous examination, innumerable, uniform-sized (1 to 3 mm), hypopigmented macules, symmetrical-

ly distributed in a speckled manner over bilateral dorsum of hands, lateral border of hands and fingers [Figure-1a], palms extending up to flexor aspect of lower one-third of forearms (less pronounced), dorsum of feet extending upto ankles (less pronounced) [Figure-1b], medial & lateral borders of feet. Occasional clustering is present. Soles are spared. On examining the mother, we found similar, less pronounced lesions on her hands and feet [Figure 2]. She was unaware of the lesions.

Figure 1: Speckled, hypopigmented macules over a) the lateral border of hands and fingers and b) the Dorsum of feet of the patient

Figure 2: Less noticeable, speckled, hypopigmented macules in the mother, over a) Dorsum of fingers and b) Feet

Systemic examination was unremarkable. There was no accentuation of skin lesions under Wood's lamp examination. Histopathological examination of a 3 mm punch biopsy from lesional skin showed a reduced number of melanocytes and diminished melanin pigment in the basal layer with only focal preservation [Figure 3].

Figure 3: Reduction in the number of melanocytes (red arrow) and focally preserved melanocytes (black arrow)

Based on the findings, the case was diagnosed as Familial Speckled Acral Hypopigmentation (FSAH). The patient did not respond to topical tacrolimus 0.1% ointment and was advised phototherapy but couldn't come due to personal reasons.

Discussion:

The various differential diagnoses of depigmentary or hypopigmentary disorders can be differentiated based on the history, clinical presentation and course of the disease [1]. Reticulate pigmentary disorders are a broad group, with significant overlap, posing a diagnostic challenge [2]. The acral reticulate pigmentary disorders include reticulate acropigmentation of Kitamura (RAPK), reticulate acropigmentation of Dohi (RAPD) aka Dyschromatosis Symmetrica Hereditaria (DSH), Dowling–Degos disease (DDD) and Dyschromatosis Universalis Hereditaria (DUH) [2,3]. While, RAPK and DDD present with hyperpigmented macules, RAPD and DUH present with both hyper and hypopigmented macules [3]. RAPK presents in the first or second decade with symmetrical, well-defined, angulated, atrophic, hyperpigmented 1-5 mm macules on the dorsum of hands and feet, sides of the neck and occasionally on the face [2,4,5]. Lesions darken over time [5]. Characteristically, they have palmar pits and breaks in dermatoglyphics. Rare cases with hypo or depigmented lesions in addition to hyperpigmented, have been reported [2]. Histopathology shows hyperkeratosis with thin and elongated rete ridges and increased basal melanin pigment [6]. A loss-of-function mutation of the ADAM10 gene was seen in some of these patients [5]. DDD presents with

symmetrical, non-atrophic, hyperpigmented, 1-4 mm macules over the flexures, inner aspects of thighs, neck and submammary regions [2,3]. Comedo-like, hyperkeratotic, follicular lesions over the face, cystic lesions and acneiform pitted scars around the mouth are also seen [2,3,5]. Rarely, in addition, widely distributed hypopigmented macules without clustering, have been reported [2]. Antler or stag horn-like branching of rete ridges is seen in histopathology. It is an autosomal dominant, rare disorder with reported mutations in the keratin 5, POGlut1 and POFUT1 genes [5].

RAPD/ DSH presents in infancy with freckle-like, angulated, hyperpigmented macules and hypo or de-pigmented macules on the hands, feet, and rarely proximal extremities and face [2]. It is an inherited disorder with a mutation in the ADAR1 gene. Neurologic manifestations and hair and dental abnormalities may be seen [5]. In DUH, non-atrophic, hyper and hypo or depigmented macules are seen all over the body [4]. There are reports of a localised form [3]. On histopathology, RAPD and DUH usually show mild hyperkeratosis, reduced basal pigmentation, pigment incontinence, and rarely reduction in the number of melanocytes [4].

Acromelanosis albo-punctata has generalised hyperpigmentation of skin with confetti-like hypopigmented macules over hands, feet and flexural areas to a lesser extent [7]. Large, depigmented macules are seen in congenital symmetric acroleukopathy over periungual areas [2]. They are neither reticulated nor speckled in character [3]. Extragenital lichen sclerosus presents with small, porcelain white, mildly atrophic

polygonal papules and plaques affecting the neck, shoulders and upper trunk [2]. Follicular plugging or loss of appendages is seen [1]. Idiopathic guttate hypomelanosis has round or oval, well-defined, depigmented macules on the extremities of adults secondary to cumulative sun exposure [1,7]. Truncal guttate hypopigmentation in Darier disease has other features, including greasy keratotic papules in seborrheic areas, acral keratoses, V-shaped scalloping of the distal part of the nail and lesions of DD over mucosa and palms. Histopathology shows uniform acantholytic clefts with corp ronds and grains [1,7].

Cole disease presents with palmoplantar hyperkeratotic papules and guttate hypopigmented macules over the trunk and extremities [7]. Guttate hypomelanosis associated with tuberous sclerosis develops during early childhood and presents as symmetrical, numerous, 1–3 mm, hypopigmented macules over the distal extremities [2]. Over time, characteristic cutaneous manifestations like hypopigmented ash-leaf macules, shagreen patches, angiofibromas and systemic manifestations develop [7].

Our patient did not have additional features or hyperpigmentation consistent with any of the differentials above. In 2005, Malakar et al. from West Bengal first reported FSAH [3]. Others have also reported familial and acquired cases of this entity [1,2,4,5,7,8]. The majority of the reports are from India. Speckled acral hypopigmentation is a novel entity, a rare form of acropigmentation. Patients present at a young age with asymptomatic, speckled hypopigmented macules on the dorsa of the hands and feet, having feathery margins [4].

The lesions do not show accentuation under a Woods lamp. A decreased or normal number of melanocytes is present [7]. An increased number of macromelanosomes was reported in some cases, unlike our case [2]. Similar to the case reported by Aldhalaan J et al., our patient too had macules extending with less severity to the distal forearms and ankles [7].

Conclusion:

Ours is probably the fifth case of FSAH, as per the literature review. As it is rare and there are very few case reports, we report one such case. Genetic testing of cases is needed to establish this as a distinct entity, possibly a variant of reticulate acropigmentation disorders and the awareness of which, prevents over diagnosis and alleviates patient's anxiety.

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